

Supplementary Material of Paper 112 (Analyses of Evolutionary Algorithms on Time-Linkage ONEMAX with General Weights)

Proof (Lemma 5). Since RLS only changes one bit for one generation, it is not difficult to see that the probability of reaching the global optimum before the number of zeros of the current solution decreases below n^c is 0. The following only discusses the $(1+1)$ EA.

It is easy to see that if one of Event I and II happens before the number of zeros of the current solution decreases below n^c , then the process will get stuck and the global optimum cannot be reached afterwards, which supports this claim. Hence, in the following, we assume that any stagnation case will not happen in the process before the number of zeros in the current solution decreases below n^c .

Let a denote the number of zeros in the current individual. Then the probability that a decreases to 0 in one generation is $(1/n^a)(1-1/n)^{n-a} \leq 1/n^a$. Let event A denote that the global optimum is reached in one generation. Since the global optimum requires $a=0$ as well as the stored first bit value of 0, we know $\Pr[A]$, the probability of reaching the global optimum in one generation, is at most $\frac{1}{n^a}$.

Let event B denote that a decreases in one generation but does not decrease to 0, and let B' be the event that $(1,0)$ first bit pattern is generated and survives. Note that B' includes the case when a does not change in one generation. As B includes the case when a decreases by 1, we have $\Pr[B] \geq \frac{a}{n} \left(1 - \frac{1}{n}\right)^{n-1} \geq \frac{a}{en}$. To estimate $\Pr[B']$, we know that the first bit must flip from 1 to 0 and at least one of 0s in the current individual must be flipped. Hence, we have $\Pr[B'] \leq \frac{1}{n} \frac{a}{n} = \frac{a}{n^2}$. Then

$$\Pr[A \mid A \cup B \cup B'] = \frac{\Pr[A]}{\Pr[A \cup B \cup B']} \leq \frac{\Pr[A]}{\Pr[B]} \leq \frac{e}{an^{a-1}} \leq \frac{e}{n^{n^c+c}}, \quad (1)$$

where the last inequality uses $a \geq n^c + 1$, and

$$\Pr[B' \mid B \cup B'] \leq \frac{\Pr[B']}{\Pr[B]} \leq \frac{e}{n}. \quad (2)$$

Via (1), we know that the probability that $B \cup B'$ (with $a \geq n^c + 1$) happens n times (if possible) before A happens once is at least

$$\left(1 - \frac{e}{n^{n^c+c}}\right)^n \geq 1 - \frac{en}{n^{n^c+c}} = 1 - \frac{e}{n^{n^c+c-1}}. \quad (3)$$

Consider the process that only B or B' happens, and let Y be the number of times that B' happens when B or B' occurs n times. Via (2), we know that Y is stochastically dominated by a random variable that follows the binomial distribution with the success probability of e/n . Then via the Chernoff bound

(See[8, (1.10.2)]), we have

$$\begin{aligned} \Pr[Y \geq e \log_2 n] &\leq \left(\frac{e^{\log_2 n - 1}}{(\log_2 n)^{\log_2 n}} \right)^e = \left(\frac{1}{e} \left(\frac{e}{\log_2 n} \right)^{\log_2 n} \right)^e \\ &\leq \left(\frac{1}{e} \frac{1}{2^{\log_2 n}} \right)^e = \frac{1}{(en)^e}, \end{aligned}$$

where the last inequality uses $\log_2 n \geq 2e$ for $n \geq 4^e$. Then with probability at least

$$1 - \frac{1}{(en)^e}, \quad (4)$$

B' happens at most $e \log_2 n - 1$ times when B or B' occurs n times.

Now we consider the situations in the next generation after B' happens. It is not difficult to see that a increases only when the current individual has $(1, 0)$ first bit pattern (that is, in the generation right after the occurrence of B') and generates an offspring with more zeros. Let B'_+ be the event that a increases by at least $\log_2 n$ or that a decreases to 0, and B'_\leq be the event that a increases by at most $\log_2 n - 1$ but does not decrease to 0. As B'_+ requires that at least $\log_2 n$ number of 1s flip or that a decreases to 0, we have

$$\begin{aligned} \Pr[B'_+] &\leq \frac{\binom{n-a}{\log_2 n}}{n^{\log_2 n}} + \frac{1}{n^a} \leq \frac{\left(\frac{e(n-a)}{\log_2 n} \right)^{\log_2 n}}{n^{\log_2 n}} + \frac{1}{n} = \left(\frac{e}{\log_2 n} \frac{n-a}{n} \right)^{\log_2 n} + \frac{1}{n} \\ &\leq \left(\frac{e}{\log_2 n} \right)^{\log_2 n} + \frac{1}{n} \leq \left(\frac{1}{2} \right)^{\log_2 n} + \frac{1}{n} = \frac{2}{n}, \end{aligned}$$

where the last inequality uses $\log_2 n \geq 2e$ for $n \geq 4^e$. For B'_\leq , we pessimistically consider the case that a does not change and have $\Pr[B'_\leq] \geq \left(1 - \frac{1}{n}\right)^n \geq \frac{1}{e} \left(1 - \frac{1}{n}\right) \geq \frac{9}{10e}$, where the last inequality uses $1 - 1/n \geq 9/10$ for $n \geq 4^e$. Then $\frac{\Pr[B'_+]}{\Pr[B'_+ \cup B'_\leq]} \leq \frac{\Pr[B'_+]}{\Pr[B'_\leq]} \leq \frac{20e}{9n}$. Hence, the probability that B'_+ does not happen once when B' occurs $e \log_2 n - 1$ times is at least

$$\left(1 - \frac{20e}{9n}\right)^{e \log_2 n - 1} \geq \left(1 - \frac{20e}{9n}\right)^{e \log_2 n} \geq 1 - \frac{20e^2 \log_2 n}{9n}. \quad (5)$$

We note here that once B'_\leq happens, a will increase by at most $\log_2 n - 1$, and that once B happens, a will decrease by at least 1. Then if B or B' occurs n times (if possible for $a \geq n^c + 1$) but B' happens at most $e \log_2 n - 1$, we have B happens at least $n - e \log_2 n + 1$. Further if only B'_\leq follows each occurrence of B' , then we know in total a decreases by at least

$$\begin{aligned} n - e \log_2 n + 1 - (e \log_2 n - 1)(\log_2 n - 1) \\ = n - (e \log_2 n - 1) \log_2 n \geq n - e \log_2^2 n \geq n - n^c, \end{aligned}$$

where the last inequality holds for n sufficiently large. That is, with these conditions, a will drop below n^c . Via (3), (4), and (5), we know that the event that a drops below n^c before reaching the global optimum, happens with probability at least

$$\begin{aligned} & \left(1 - \frac{e}{n^{n^c+c-1}}\right) \left(1 - \frac{1}{(en)^e}\right) \left(1 - \frac{20e^2 \log_2 n}{9n}\right) \\ & \geq 1 - \frac{e}{n^{n^c+c-1}} - \frac{1}{(en)^e} - \frac{20e^2 \log_2 n}{9n} \geq 1 - \frac{17 \log_2 n}{n}, \end{aligned}$$

where the last inequality uses $e/n^{n^c+c-1} \leq e/n$ for $n \geq 2^{1/c}$, $1/(en)^e \leq 1/n$, and $(e+1)/\log_2 n + 20e^2/9 \leq 17$ for $n \geq 4^e$.

Proof (Lemma 7). For RLS, if $w \in [-n..-2]$, then from Lemma 3, Event I already happens, and thus this lemma trivially holds. In the following, we consider RLS for $w = -1$ and (1+1) EA for $w \in [-n..-1]$.

Let a be the number of zeros in X^{t_0} . If $a \leq -w - 1$, then we know that $|X_{[2..n]}^{t_0}| = n - a - 1 \geq n + w$, that is, Event I happens.

If $a = -w$, then $f(X^{t_0-1}, X^{t_0}) = n + w$. For any generated offspring with the first bit value of 0, it will have a fitness value at most $n - 1 + w$, which is less than its parent $X^{(g_0)} = X^{t_0}$, hence cannot enter into the next generation. The only case that the offspring can be accepted is 1^n , which means that Event II happens.

If $a \geq -w + 1$, then for (1+1) EA, it is not difficult to see that the probability of changing the first bit pattern to (1, 0) is at most $\binom{a}{-w+1} \frac{1}{n^{-w+1}} \frac{1}{n}$, and also not difficult to see that the probability of changing the first bit pattern to (1, 1) is at least $\binom{a}{-w} \frac{1}{n^{-w}} \left(1 - \frac{1}{n}\right)^{n+w}$. Hence, conditional on that the first bit pattern changes (that is, (1, 0) or (1, 1) happens), the probability of the first bit pattern changing to (1, 1) is at least

$$\frac{1}{1 + \frac{\binom{a}{-w+1} \frac{1}{n^{-w+1}} \frac{1}{n}}{\binom{a}{-w} \frac{1}{n^{-w}} \left(1 - \frac{1}{n}\right)^{n+w}}} = \frac{1}{1 + \frac{(a+w)e}{(1-w)n^2}} \geq \frac{1}{1 + \frac{(n^c+w)e}{(1-w)n^2}} \geq \frac{1}{1 + \frac{(n^c-0)e}{(1-0)n^2}} \geq 1 - \frac{e}{n^{2-c}},$$

where the first inequality uses $a \leq n^c$, and the penultimate inequality uses $w \leq -1 < 0$. For RLS and $w = -1$, the first bit pattern can only change to (1, 1) because one zero bit in $X^{(g_0)} = X^{t_0}$ needs to be flipped to ensure $\tilde{X}^{(g_0)}$ has equal fitness to $X^{(g_0)}$ and thus enters into the next generation. Hence, the above lower bound of the conditional probability also holds.

We note that the process after the first bit pattern changes to (1, 1) turns to the case discussed in Lemma 6. Hence, we know the probability that Event II happens is at least

$$\left(1 - \frac{e}{n^{2-c}}\right) \left(1 - \frac{1}{n^{1-2c}} - (n-1)e^{-\frac{n^c}{e}}\right) \geq 1 - \frac{e}{n^{2-c}} - \frac{1}{n^{1-2c}} - (n-1)e^{-\frac{n^c}{e}}.$$

Proof (Lemma 8). We discuss the process until there is 1 zero or the first bit changes to 1, conditional on that when the number of ones in the current individual changes, it only increases by 1 (noting that this condition holds trivially for the RLS), which happens with probability at least $\prod_{a=n^c}^2 (1 - \frac{ea}{n}) \geq (1 - \frac{e}{n^{1-c}})^{n^c} \geq 1 - \frac{e}{n^{1-2c}}$, where we use $a \leq n^c$ and Lemma 1 to obtain the above first expression. When the number of ones increases by 1, by Lemma 1, we calculate the probability of the event that the first bit value stays at 0 until there is 1 zero in the current individual $\prod_{a=n^c}^2 (1 - \frac{1}{a}) = \frac{1}{n^c}$. Hence, we know that the event that the first bit changes to 1 before a changes to 1 happens with probability at least $(1 - \frac{e}{n^{1-2c}}) (1 - \frac{1}{n^c}) \geq 1 - \frac{e}{n^{1-2c}} - \frac{1}{n^c}$. Let \tilde{g} be the generation for the first time the first bit changes to 1 and let \tilde{t} be the corresponding decision time. If $|X_{[2..n]}^{\tilde{t}}| \in [w + n..n - 2]$, then Event I happens. Otherwise, the process afterwards turns to the case discussed in Lemma 7, and we know that Event I or II happens with probability at least $1 - \frac{e}{n^{2-c}} - \frac{1}{n^{1-2c}} - ne^{-\frac{n^c}{e}}$. Hence, the overall probability for the current case that Event I or II happens is at least

$$\begin{aligned} & \min \left\{ 1 - \frac{e}{n^{1-2c}} - \frac{1}{n^c}, 1 - \frac{e}{n^{2-c}} - \frac{1}{n^{1-2c}} - (n-1)e^{-\frac{n^c}{e}} \right\} \\ & \geq 1 - \frac{e}{n^{1-2c}} - \frac{1}{n^c} - (n-1)e^{-\frac{n^c}{e}}, \end{aligned}$$

where the last inequality uses that for $n \geq 2$, $e/n^{1+c} + 1 \leq e$, and thus $\frac{e}{n^{2-c}} + \frac{1}{n^{1-2c}} = \frac{1}{n^{1-2c}} (\frac{e}{n^{1+c}} + 1) \leq \frac{e}{n^{1-2c}}$.

Proof (Lemma 9). For the RLS, since only one bit can be flipped for each generation, we know that $X_{[2..n]}^{(g_0)} = X_{[2..n]}^{t_0} \neq 1^{n-1}$, and thus $\tilde{X}^{(g_0)}$ cannot be the global optimum. Hence, the first bit pattern afterwards turns to $(0, 0)$ or $(0, 1)$.

For the $(1+1)$ EA, starting from $X_1^{(g_0)} = X_1^{t_0} = 0$, we know that the probability of generating offspring with fewer zeros is at most $n^c/n = 1/n^{1-c}$, and that the probability to generate an offspring that can enter into the next generation is at least $(1 - 1/n)^{n-a} \geq (1 - 1/n)^{n-1} \geq 1/e$ for a the number of zeros in $X^{(g_0)}$ (here we pessimistically consider generating the offspring with no 1 from its parent changing to 0, which will surely enter into the next generation). Hence, if the offspring enters into the next generation, then with probability at most $(1/n^{1-c})/(1/e) = e/n^{1-c}$, an offspring with fewer zeros can be reached. Hence, with probability of at least $1 - e/n^{1-c}$, the global optimum cannot be reached and the first bit pattern turns to $(0, 0)$ or $(0, 1)$.

Hence, from Lemmata 7 and 8, we prove this lemma.

Proof (Theorem 3). For the random initialization, we know $E[|X^1|] = n/2$. With the Chernoff inequality, we know $\Pr[|X^1| \leq bn] \leq \exp\left(-\frac{(1-2b)^2}{2}n\right)$. Together with Lemma 5, we know that the global optimum cannot be reached before the number of zeros in the current solution decreases below n^c with probability at least $\left(1 - \exp\left(-\frac{(1-2b)^2}{2}n\right)\right) \left(1 - \frac{4e}{5}n(1-b)^{n^c}\right)$. Let g_0 be such first generation and t_0 be the corresponding decision time. We know that there are only four cases

for the first bit pattern of $(X_1^{t_0-1}, X_1^{t_0})$, $(0, 0)$, $(0, 1)$, $(1, 0)$, and $(1, 1)$. Therefore, from Lemmata 6 to 9, we know that the probability that Event I or II happens is at least

$$\begin{aligned} & \left(1 - \exp\left(-\frac{(1-2b)^2}{2}n\right)\right) \left(1 - \frac{4e}{5}n(1-b)^{n^c}\right) \\ & \quad \left(1 - \frac{e}{n^{1-2c}} - \frac{1}{n^c} - \frac{n-1}{e^{\frac{nc}{e}}} - \frac{e}{n^{1-c}}\right) \\ & \geq 1 - \exp\left(-\frac{(1-2b)^2}{2}n\right) - \frac{4e}{5}n(1-b)^{n^c} - \\ & \quad \frac{e}{n^{1-2c}} - \frac{1}{n^c} - (n-1)e^{-\frac{nc}{e}} - \frac{e}{n^{1-c}}. \end{aligned}$$

Taking $b = 1/4$ and $c = 1/3$, we have the lower bound of the probability of the non-convergence to the global optimum as

$$\begin{aligned} & 1 - \exp\left(-\frac{1}{8}n\right) - \frac{17\log_2 n}{n} - \frac{e}{n^{1/3}} - \frac{1}{n^{1/3}} - (n-1)e^{-\frac{n^{1/3}}{e}} - \frac{e}{n^{2/3}} \\ & \geq 1 - n \exp\left(-\frac{n^{1/3}}{e}\right) - \frac{4}{n^{1/3}}, \end{aligned}$$

where the inequality uses $-n/8 < -n^{1/3}/e$ and $(17\log_2 n/n^{2/3}) + (e/n^{1/3}) \leq 3 - e$ for n sufficiently large.

Proof (Lemma 10). For the $(1+1)$ EA, if Event III happens (say at generation g_0), then $X^{(g_0)} = X^{t_0}$ will have the fitness of at least $n+1$. However, from $X_1^{(g_0)} = 0$ we know that any offspring $\tilde{X}^{(g_0)}$ will have the fitness value of at most $n < n+1$. Hence, $\tilde{X}^{(g_0)}$ cannot replace $X^{(g_0)}$, and then the stagnation happens.

For the RLS, if Event III happens (say at generation g_0), then with $w \geq 2$ we know $\tilde{X}^{(g_0)}$ has the fitness of at most $|X^{(g_0)}| + 1 < |X^{(g_0)}| + w$, that is, it has a fitness less than its parent $X^{(g_0)}$, and thus cannot enter into the next generation. Hence, the stagnation happens.

Proof (Lemma 11). Since the RLS only flips one bit each generation, we know that if the first bit flips to 0, then the generated offspring $\tilde{X}^{(g)}$ has the fitness of $|\tilde{X}^{(g)}| = |X^{(g)}| - 1 < |X^{(g)}| + w$, which is the fitness of $X^{(g)}$, and thus $\tilde{X}^{(g)}$ cannot enter into the next generation. That is, the first bit value stays at 1 and eventually the global optimum is reached. The first part is proved.

Now we consider the $(1+1)$ EA. Let a denote the number of zeros in the current individual. Let the event C denote that the generated offspring has more number of ones and its first bit value is 1. Then we know $\Pr[C] \geq \frac{a}{n} \left(1 - \frac{1}{n}\right)^{n-1} \geq \frac{a}{en}$. It is easy to see that such offspring will enter into the next generation due to the selection operator. On the other hand, let the event D denote that the offspring with the first bit value of 0 generated from a parent with first bit value of 1, enters into the next generation, and we know $\Pr[D] \leq \frac{1}{n} \frac{a}{n}$. Hence,

$\frac{\Pr[C]}{\Pr[D]} \geq \frac{n}{e}$, and thus we know that the probability that C happens $(1-b)n$ times before D happens is at least

$$\left(1 - \frac{e}{n+e}\right)^{(1-b)n} = \left(1 - \frac{1}{n/e+1}\right)^{\frac{n}{e}(1-b)e} \geq \frac{1}{e^{(1-b)e}}. \quad (6)$$

Since $|X^1| \geq bn$, we know that the event that C happens $(1-b)n$ times will result in reaching the global optimum, and thus the global convergence probability of the $(1+1)$ EA is derived.

We now discuss the non-global-convergence part. Let a_0 be the number of zeros in X^1 . If $a_0 \leq w-1$, then we consider the process afterwards. Otherwise, from the above analysis, we know that $1/e^{(1-b)e}$ in (6) is also the lower bound of the probability that C happens $(1-b)n-w+1$ times before D happens once, and thus also the lower bound for the event that the first bit value stays at 1 till the first time the number of zeros is less than w . We further show that the number of zeros is at least $w/2$ with a high probability the first time it drops below w . Let $a \geq w$ denote the number of zeros in a solution with the first bit value of 1 before it drops below w , and conditional on its offspring with the first bit value of 1, let H denote the event that the offspring has the number of zeros less than a , and G the event that the offspring has the number of zeros at least $a/2$. If $a = 2$, from Lemma 1, we know

$$\frac{\Pr[G]}{\Pr[H]} \geq 1 - \frac{ae}{n-1} = 1 - \frac{2e}{n-1}. \quad (7)$$

For $a > 2$, we have $\Pr[H] \geq \frac{a}{n} \left(1 - \frac{1}{n}\right)^{n-2} \geq \frac{a}{en}$, and $\Pr[G] \geq \Pr[H] - \frac{\binom{a}{a/2}}{n^{a/2}}$. Hence,

$$\frac{\Pr[G]}{\Pr[H]} \geq \frac{\Pr[H] - \frac{\binom{a}{a/2}}{n^{a/2}}}{\Pr[H]} = 1 - \frac{\binom{a}{a/2}}{\Pr[H] n^{a/2}} \geq 1 - \frac{\left(\frac{2e}{n}\right)^{a/2}}{\frac{a}{en}} \geq 1 - \frac{\left(\frac{2e}{n}\right)^{3/2}}{\frac{3}{en}} \geq 1 - \frac{e^3}{n^{1/2}},$$

where the second inequality uses $\binom{n}{k} \leq (en/k)^k$, the third inequality uses $a \geq 3$, and the last inequality uses $2 < e < 3$. Thus together with (7), we have

$$\frac{\Pr[G]}{\Pr[H]} \geq \min \left\{ 1 - \frac{2e}{n-1}, 1 - \frac{e^3}{n^{1/2}} \right\} = 1 - \frac{e^3}{n^{1/2}}. \quad (8)$$

That is, with probability at least $1 - \frac{e^3}{n^{1/2}}$, there are at least $w/2$ zeros in the starting solution when the number of zeros drops below w for the first time. We now reuse a be the number of zeros in the current solution, and consider $a \geq w/2$ in the following. Recall that C is the event that the generated offspring has more number of ones and its first bit value is 1, and D the event that the offspring with the first bit value of 0 generated from a parent with first bit value of 1, enters into the next generation. It is not difficult to see that $\Pr[C] \leq \frac{a}{n}$ and $\Pr[D] \geq \frac{1}{n} \frac{a}{n} \left(1 - \frac{1}{n}\right)^{n-2} \geq \frac{a}{en^2}$. Hence, we have $\frac{\Pr[D]}{\Pr[C]} \geq \frac{1}{en}$. Thus, we know that

the probability that D happens once before C happens $\min\{a_0, w/2\}$ times is at least

$$1 - \left(1 - \frac{1}{en + 1}\right)^{\min\{a_0, w/2\}} \geq \frac{1}{1 + \frac{en+1}{\min\{a_0, w/2\}}},$$

where the last inequality uses $1 - (1 - x)^n \geq 1/(1 + 1/(xm))$ for $x \in (0, 1]$ and $m > 0$, which is proven in [1, Lemma 2] and also in [7, Lemma 31].

Together with the above discussed probability of at least $1/e^{(1-b)e}$ for this condition that the first bit value stays at 1 till the first time the number of zeros is less than w , and (8), the non-global-convergence probability for the $(1+1)$ EA is derived.

Proof (Lemma 12). For the RLS, from $(X_1^0, X_1^1) = (0, 1)$, we know that with probability of $1 - 1/n$, the generated $\tilde{X}^{(g)}$ has its first bit value of 1, which has better fitness than its parent $X^{(g)}$ and surely enters into the next generation. Then it turns to the $(1, 1)$ case. Together with Lemma 11, the first part is proved.

Now we consider the $(1+1)$ EA. We know that with probability of at least $(1 - \frac{1}{n})^n \geq (1 - \frac{1}{n}) \frac{1}{e}$, the generated $\tilde{X}^{(g)}$ has at least the same number of ones as its parent $X^{(g)}$ and has its first bit value of 1. Due to definition, we know $f(\tilde{X}^{(g)}) \geq f(X^{(g)}) + w \geq f(X^{(g)})$, thus it will enter into the next generation, that is, $X^{(g+1)} = \tilde{X}^{(g)}$, and thus $X_1^{(g+1)} = \tilde{X}_1^{(g)} = 1$. Hence, together with Lemma 11, the $(1+1)$ EA part in this lemma is proved.

Proof (Lemma 14). The RLS part and the first part for the $(1+1)$ EA in this lemma are trivial from the definition of Event III.

For the second part of the $(1+1)$ EA, since Event III doesn't happen in the first generation, we only need to generate an offspring with at least $w + |X_{[2..n]}^1|$ number of ones, which is possible, and it will have the same or better fitness compared with $f(X^0, X^1) = w + |X_{[2..n]}^1|$, and thus surely enter into the next generation. Once new offspring enters into the next generation, the first bit pattern becomes either $(0, 1)$ or $(0, 0)$. Then together with Lemmata 12 and 13, we prove the convergence results.

Moreover, it is not difficult to see that generating an offspring to leave the $(1, 0)$ pattern happens with probability at most $\frac{\binom{n-k+1}{w}}{n^w} \leq \left(\frac{e(n-k+1)}{nw}\right)^w$, thus we need at least $\left(\frac{nw}{e(n-k+1)}\right)^w \geq \left(\frac{1}{(1-b)e}\right)^w$ expected iterations.

Proof (Theorem 4). The results for the RLS is directly from Lemmata 11 to 13. For the expected runtime conditional on $(X_1^0, X_1^1) \neq (1, 0)$, a simple coupon collector process then results in $\Theta(n \log n)$ expected runtime.

Now we consider the $(1+1)$ EA. For the random initialization, we know that $E[|X^1|] = n/2$. With Chernoff bound [8, Corollary 1.10.6], we have

$$\Pr[|X^1| \in [bn..(1-b)n]] \geq 1 - 2 \exp\left(-\frac{(1-2b)^2 n}{6}\right). \quad (9)$$

Since there are only four possible cases for (X_1^0, X_1^1) with equal probability of $1/4$, $(0, 0)$, $(0, 1)$, $(1, 0)$, and $(1, 1)$, from Lemmata 11 to 13, we know that the probability for the algorithm to reach the global optimum of the ONEMAX_w function is at least

$$\begin{aligned} & \left(1 - 2 \exp\left(-\frac{(1-2b)^2 n}{6}\right)\right) \\ & \frac{1}{4} \left(e^{-(1-b)e} + \left(1 - \frac{1}{n}\right) e^{-(1-b)e-1} + \left(1 - \frac{1}{n}\right) e^{-(1-b)e-1} \right) \\ & = \frac{1}{4e^{(1-b)e+1}} \left(1 - 2 \exp\left(-\frac{(1-2b)^2 n}{6}\right)\right) \left(e + 2 - \frac{2}{n}\right). \end{aligned}$$

Taking $b = 1/4$, we have derived the global convergence probability for the $(1+1)$ EA.

Essentially, the above probability for the global convergence is for the process that the first bit value stays at 1 once it is generated and the global optimum is eventually reached. Consider the process conditional on the above event. It is not difficult to see that before the first bit reaches the value of 1, the conditional process is identical to the original one, and after that the conditional process is identical to the one of the $(1+1)$ EA optimizing the $(n-1)$ -dimensional ONEMAX function. Hence, the runtime for the conditional process is $\Theta(n \log n)$.

For the non-global-convergence result, we consider the cases of $(X_1^0, X_1^1) = (1, 1)$ and $(0, 1)$ from Lemmata 11 and 12, and with (9) for $|X^1| \leq (1-b)n$, the non-global convergence probability is at least

$$\begin{aligned} & \left(1 - 2 \exp\left(-\frac{(1-2b)^2 n}{6}\right)\right) \frac{1}{4} \left(\frac{e^{-(1-b)e}(1 - e^3/n^{1/2})}{1 + \frac{en+1}{\min\{n-|X^1|, w/2\}}} \right. \\ & \quad \left. + \left(1 - \frac{1}{n}\right) \frac{e^{-(1-b)e-1}(1 - e^3/n^{1/2})}{1 + \frac{en+1}{\min\{n-|X^1|, w/2\}}} \right) \\ & = \frac{1}{4} \left(1 - 2 \exp\left(-\frac{(1-2b)^2 n}{6}\right)\right) \cdot \left(1 + \frac{1}{e} \left(1 - \frac{1}{n}\right)\right) \frac{e^{-(1-b)e}(1 - e^3/n^{1/2})}{1 + \frac{en+1}{\min\{n-|X^1|, w/2\}}} \\ & \geq \left(1 - 2 \exp\left(-\frac{(1-2b)^2 n}{6}\right) - \frac{e^3}{n^{1/2}}\right) \cdot \frac{\left(1 + \frac{1}{e} \left(1 - \frac{1}{2}\right)\right) e^{-(1-b)e}}{4 \left(1 + \frac{en+1}{\min\{bn, w/2\}}\right)} \\ & \geq \left(1 - \frac{22}{n^{1/2}}\right) \frac{\frac{2e+1}{2e} e^{-(1-b)e}}{4 \left(1 + \frac{en+1}{\min\{bn, w/2\}}\right)} = \left(1 - \frac{22}{n^{1/2}}\right) \frac{\frac{2e+1}{8} e^{-(1-b)e-1}}{1 + \frac{en+1}{\min\{bn, w/2\}}}, \end{aligned}$$

where the first inequality uses $|X^1| \leq (1/2+b)n$ and $n \geq 2$, and the last inequality uses $2 \exp(-(1-2b)^2 n/6) \leq (22 - e^3)/n^{1/2}$ for constant b and sufficiently large n . Taking $b = 1/4$ and $n \geq 500$ the theorem is proved.

Proof (Lemma 15). The key is to show that for any two $w_1 \leq w_2 \in \mathbb{Z}_{<-n}$ and any $i, j \in \{1, \dots, M\}$, $f_{w_1}(X_i, Y_i) \leq f_{w_1}(X_j, Y_j) \Leftrightarrow f_{w_2}(X_i, Y_i) \leq f_{w_2}(X_j, Y_j)$.

Note that

$$\begin{aligned}
f_w(X_i, Y_i) &\leq f_w(X_j, Y_j) \\
\Leftrightarrow wX_{i,1} + \sum_{k=1}^n Y_{i,k} &\leq wX_{j,1} + \sum_{k=1}^n Y_{j,k} \\
\Leftrightarrow w(X_{i,1} - X_{j,1}) &\leq \sum_{k=1}^n Y_{j,k} - \sum_{k=1}^n Y_{i,k}.
\end{aligned} \tag{10}$$

Obviously, if $f_w(X_i, Y_i) \leq f_w(X_j, Y_j)$, then $X_{i,1} \geq X_{j,1}$. Otherwise, since $w \leq -n$, we have $w(X_{i,1} - X_{j,1}) > -w \geq n \geq \sum_{k=1}^n Y_{j,k}$, which contradicts to $w(X_{i,1} - X_{j,1}) \leq \sum_{k=1}^n Y_{j,k} - \sum_{k=1}^n Y_{i,k}$. Hence, the event that $X_{i,1} = 0, X_{j,1} = 1$ cannot happen for $f_w(X_i, Y_i) \leq f_w(X_j, Y_j)$.

If $X_{i,1} = X_{j,1}$, then if $f_{w_1}(X_i, Y_i) \leq f_{w_1}(X_j, Y_j)$, we have $\sum_{k=1}^n Y_{j,k} - \sum_{k=1}^n Y_{i,k} \geq 0 = w_2(X_{i,1} - X_{j,1})$, that is, $f_{w_2}(X_i, Y_i) \leq f_{w_2}(X_j, Y_j)$. Vice versa.

If $X_{i,1} = 1, X_{j,1} = 0$, (10) is equivalent to $w \leq \sum_{k=1}^n Y_{j,k} - \sum_{k=1}^n Y_{i,k}$. Since $\sum_{k=1}^n Y_{j,k} - \sum_{k=1}^n Y_{i,k} \geq -\sum_{k=1}^n Y_{i,k} \geq -n$, we know that the above inequality holds for all $w \leq -n$.